

Estimating the Monetary Value of a QALY in Germany

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Evaluating the outcomes of cost-effectiveness analyses of health interventions requires an appropriate threshold value. One possible source for such a threshold is an estimate of the monetary value of a quality-adjusted life-year (QALY), as for instance used in the Netherlands and Sweden. These estimates are typically obtained through stated preference elicitation, e.g. willingness to pay experiments. Our study adds to the literature by choosing a different approach and, to the best of our knowledge, providing the first monetary QALY valuations for Germany on the basis of a well-being valuation approach.

Methods: We applied a well-being valuation method to general health, using life satisfaction data as a proxy for experienced utility and the marginal rate of substitution between health and income to estimate a monetary value of health. The German Socioeconomic Panel, a nationally representative longitudinal survey, was used. We constructed SF-6D health utilities for 33,490 individuals answering the SF-12 questionnaire. To exploit the panel structure of our data a fixed effects regression was employed. Several robustness checks were conducted to explore differences across subgroups and the sensitivity of our results to changes in underlying assumptions.

Results: Results from the fixed effects regression using household equivalized income in a linear form resulted in an implied monetary value of a QALY of € 63,456 in the German population. Considerable differences were found between age groups with QALY values of € 44,199 and € 92,242 for individuals aged below and above 50 respectively. Gender affected estimates with monetary QALY values of € 69,774 for females and € 56,690 for males. Using raw net instead of equivalized household income lead to a QALY value of € 107,883. In former East Germany the monetary value of a QALY was estimated to be € 21,978 and in former West Germany € 78,588. This discrepancy is attributed to a higher observed impact of income and a lower observed impact of health on life satisfaction in former East Germany.

Discussion: The value of a QALY in Germany found in this study is consistent with values found in studies in other countries in Europe. Despite QALYs not being used in cost-effectiveness analyses in Germany, our study provides insight to policy makers about the value of benefits generated in the health care sector. It also provides further evidence on the general applicability of the well-being valuation method for estimating the monetary value of a QALY. The considerable differences in value observed between age groups and regions emphasize the importance of discussing the appropriateness and normative implications of using a single (average) threshold value as guidance for reimbursement decisions in health care.